

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SPEECH AND THINKING BASED ON NATIVE LANGUAGE LESSONS IN PRIMARY GRADES.

Burkhanov Zavqiddin Sherali oglu

Researcher of Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the role of native language lessons in developing speech and thinking of primary school students, effective methods and techniques for their development. The importance of innovative methods, interactive approaches and a system of didactic exercises in developing speech culture, logical thinking, expanding vocabulary and forming independent expression skills is highlighted.

Primary school is a period of intensive formation of a child's personality, speech and thinking. Therefore, native language lessons are not only a means of imparting grammatical knowledge, but also an important means of developing thinking, communication and creativity in students. Through the correct development of speech, students' thinking expands, the ability to perform logical analysis, and express thoughts clearly in words is formed. In order for native language lessons to be socially useful, they should be focused on forming in students the skills of grammatically correct, stylistically clear, consistent expression of their thoughts and the ability to convey the thoughts of others. The instruction for developing speech in native language classes requires the use of methodological methods that allow students to understand the role of each word group or part of speech in our language when teaching grammatical material, that is, grammatical theory is taught in order to develop grammatically correct and clear speech skills, and to develop comprehension and writing skills.

The development of children's speech in the lesson is reflected in the content of the lesson and the types of tasks used. Connecting the study of grammatical, word-forming, and spelling materials with the development of speech is the management of students' mental activity. The process of developing children's speech is associated with the development of their thinking. The native language lesson is evaluated based on the fact that it is aimed at working on the development of students' thinking. This means conducting exercises that require mental activity in the process of studying specific grammatical and spelling material, ensuring better assimilation of this material. For example, to form the concept of "cognate words", it is necessary to compare the lexical meaning and morphemic composition of words (their common meaning and the presence of the same root in them) necessary. In order to develop students' thinking, the teacher, when preparing for the lesson, selects the types of tasks, determines the material of the lesson and the mental exercises that students will

perform in mastering it. The theoretical knowledge given to students allows them to use the language consciously.

Types and structure of lessons in the native language. Types of lessons are determined by the didactic purpose, such as: a lesson of learning new material, a lesson of consolidating knowledge, a generalizing-repetition lesson, a lesson of taking into account (checking) the extent to which knowledge has been mastered, etc. Each type of lesson differs from the other in its specific structure. There is a certain connection between the didactic purpose, type and structure of the lesson. The didactic purpose of a particular lesson is determined depending on the topic being studied and the place of this lesson in the system of lessons. The teacher selects the type of lesson and determines its structure, taking into account the number of hours allocated to the topic in the program and the characteristics of the material to be studied. There can be no strict template for the construction of a lesson. However, observing the stages of checking homework, repeating, explaining new material, consolidating, and assigning homework in a lesson has proven itself in practice. Nevertheless, the teacher should decide on which stage (explaining new material, completing independent work, or checking homework) to start the lesson, based on the creative approach to these, the purpose of the lesson, and the methodological methods used, and not forget that it is of great importance to clearly define the working connection between the stages and the content of the work at each stage. Combining all stages of the lesson into one process requires high skill from the teacher. If students are taught to work independently in a modular way starting from the first grade, it will be easier to organize similar lessons in subsequent grades, as students will gradually develop skills in this regard. The teacher should also organize moments of relaxation during the lesson. Below is an example of a 1-hour native language lesson based on one of the new pedagogical technologies - a module:

Lesson topic. Words denoting persons and things.

Lesson objective. To provide students with knowledge about words denoting persons and things, to teach them to express their thoughts clearly, correctly and expressively, to develop writing skills based on cursive writing.

Lesson type. New educational lesson

Lesson equipment. Flashcards, test tasks, color pictures.

Didactic goal of the module. To ensure that students work independently in small groups, develop the skills of distinguishing and grouping words according to their meaning, and master the correct pronunciation and spelling of words denoting persons and things. Objective. To consolidate students' knowledge of words denoting persons and things.

Method. Conversation and independent work

Assignments:

1. Explain the condition of exercise 92.
2. Read the poem expressively.
3. Ask questions to the highlighted words. What do they mean?
4. Find synonyms for the words "Miti", "Oshiyon".
5. Educational game:
 - a) divide the birds and flowers into two groups;
 - b) take a picture of a bird in your hand and say its name;

d) take a picture of a flower in your hand and say its name.

6. Complete the test tasks:

I. Mark the answer where the name of the person is given.

A. Mirzo Babur B. Bird

II. Mark the line where the word denoting the thing is given.

A. Pen B. Amir Temur

A generalizing lesson is a special type of grammar lesson. In this lesson, the knowledge gained in the process of studying a topic or section is systematized. In order for this lesson not to become a lesson of repeating some theoretical material studied in previous lessons, types of work are used that require comparing what has been learned.

Generalizing lessons are diverse in their structure, and according to the results of experiments, the following option is approved:

1. Working on exercises aimed at applying knowledge about the existing features of the studied grammatical concept.

2. Generalizing and checking knowledge.

3. Independent creative work.

Sample generalizing lesson

Topic. Word groups (generalization).

The purpose of the lesson: To consolidate knowledge about the properties of nouns, adjectives, numerals, pronouns and verbs, to develop the skills of recognizing them and using them correctly.

Lesson progress

I. Vocabulary work.

— Write the following in one word:

1. The dearest person (mother)

2. Going to the museum as a group (excursion)

3. Underground castle in big cities (metro)

4. Source of knowledge (book)

— Now write the following words: bread, water, house, ...

Compare these words with your previous words. Which of them appeared first? Why do you think so?

II. Observing word groups and their signs.

— How do words arise?

— When people invent something new, they give it a name. In this way, a new name is formed in the language.

— Think about how people would communicate with each other if everything did not have a name and answer.

— If things did not have names, it would be very difficult for people to explain something to each other. In this case, it would be necessary to show the thing itself or a picture. Words that name things greatly help people communicate.

— Do words only name people and things?

— No. They also indicate the signs, actions, and numbers of things.

— What are all the groups of words in our language called?

- They are called word groups.
- Name the word groups that you have learned.
- Noun, adjective, number, pronoun, verb.
- Remember their characteristics and fill in the table below.

The importance of methodological teaching of the content of the native language in schools corresponds to the task set by our state for schools at the current stage of development of society. These tasks are multifaceted, and their implementation is aimed at raising the consciousness of students, providing them with ideological and political, moral, aesthetic and labor education. As a result of teaching the native language, students develop the skills to express their thoughts grammatically correct, stylistically clear, meaningful, in tone, and to write them correctly in spelling. This task is a specific feature of the Uzbek language as a subject of study and is implemented in connection with the tasks of general education aimed at forming the student as a person. The content of the knowledge provided in the content of native language education is knowledge about the sound structure of the Uzbek language and the methods of expressing sounds in written speech (phonetic and graphic); about the change of words and the connection of words in a sentence (grammatical, i.e. morphological and syntactic); about the morphemic composition of words and methods of word formation (concerning word formation); about the lexical-semantic group of words (lexicological); about the principles of correct writing of the Uzbek language and the use of punctuation marks (orthographic and punctuation). This knowledge is manifested, firstly, in grammatical, phonetic, word formation concepts, and secondly, in graphic, orthographic, punctuation rules. In addition, the Uzbek language course also includes phonetic, graphic, morphological, syntactic and other skills and qualifications. In the process of learning a language, students also work on developing skills common to many other subjects (cross-curricular skills).

In pedagogy, such interdisciplinary skills include analysis, synthesis, abstraction (imagining language phenomena), generalization, grouping, comparison, etc. Purposeful work on the formation of these skills in students allows them to activate their educational activities and successfully acquire knowledge. Special skills acquired in the mother tongue course and interdisciplinary skills are formed in the educational process without separating from each other. The knowledge provided and the special skills acquired in students are recorded in school programs and state educational standards. Knowledge that provides a basis for conscious acquisition of the language and the formation of graphic and spelling skills in students has been selected for study in primary grades. In the field of phonetics and graphics, students acquire knowledge that allows them to correctly understand the sound composition of a word, the specific characteristics of vowels and consonants, the importance of sound in distinguishing meaning in a word, and also create the opportunity for them to consciously determine the relationship (connection) between the sound and graphic form of a word, and to write a word correctly. From the field of morphology, knowledge of great practical importance for the conscious assimilation of a word and its correct use has been selected. Starting from the 1st grade, elementary school students study word classes (noun, adjective, numeral, pronoun, verb) at different levels. From syntax, the program includes knowledge about a sentence as a speech unit, the connection of words in a sentence, and primary and

secondary parts. Information on the morphemic composition of a word is provided in sufficient detail to enable elementary school students to understand the important features of each morpheme, their significance, and their interaction with each other in a word and to use them to spell words correctly.

The program does not provide a separate section on “Vocabulary”, but students learn about lexical-semantic groups of words (synonyms, antonyms), their lexical meanings, word classes and word structure in the process of studying them. The primary school native language course is structured taking into account the interconnected study of all aspects of the language in grades 1-4, and elementary knowledge of phonetics, lexis, grammar and word formation is provided in each grade. Such a structure of the course requires the study of all aspects of the language as a whole phenomenon that interacts with each other. Such an approach to language learning allows you to direct the educational process to solving the task of developing students' speech. The “Grammar, Spelling and Speech Development” section of the program includes the following sections in each grade: “Sounds and Letters”, “Word”, “Speech”, “Connected Speech”. The main topics are studied in every four grades, based on the principle of gradual consistency. Leading topics are allocated in each grade. In the 1st grade, a large place is given to the study of topics related to phonetics and graphics, as students master the process of reading and writing. In the 3rd grade, the study of the morphemic composition of the word and the sentence is important.

Based on knowledge about word formation, students develop a conscious attitude to the lexical meaning of the word and its use in speech. In the 4th grade, the study of word groups is given priority (morphological knowledge is deepened, the skills of correctly writing possessive and accusative suffixes of nouns, and accusative suffixes of verbs are formed). Work on connected speech is carried out on a planned basis for four years in conjunction with the study of grammatical and orthographic materials. In native language lessons, language phenomena are studied in terms of their meaning (semantics), structure, and function. Since the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence, it has put a policy of reforming society on the agenda. As in all areas, the policy of reforming the education sector has also begun to be consistently implemented. The new edition of the State Educational Standard for Primary Education also emerged as a result of experiences during the period of independence.

It is playing a programmatic role in creating a new generation of primary education textbooks and methodological manuals. The “Introduction” section of the State Educational Standard for Primary Education specifically states that “The primary education process teaches the student to form the ability to think logically, develop intellectually, develop a worldview, develop communicative literacy and self-awareness, to be physically healthy, to feel the beauties of material existence, to enjoy beauty and elegance, to assimilate and respect national traditions, and to observe them.” The implementation of such requirements for primary education requires a clear definition of the content of education and a new approach to teaching. As stated in the State Educational Standard, “The requirements set by the state and society at the stage of primary education” should fully ensure mutual compliance, proportionality, and harmony across educational areas. In this regard, the establishment of a primary educational standard allows for the modernization of the structure of the educational process and the content of the components of the same structure, the use of new, modern

pedagogical technologies in the process of primary education. The content of mother tongue education in primary grades is determined based on the requirements set for this stage of education.

References:

- 1.Yembergenova A.A. Methodology for improving the spelling literacy of primary school students in native language classes (on the example of schools where education is conducted in the Karakalpak language) Ped. fan. fal. (PhD) doc. ... diss. abstract. – Nukus.: 2023. – 52 p.,
- 2.Azimova I., Mavlonova K., Kuronov S., Tursun Sh. Native language and reading literacy. Textbooks for grades 1-2-3-4. –T.: 2021.-118 p.,
- 3.Ikromova R., Gulomova Kh., Yoldasheva Sh., Shodmonkulova D. (For primary education) Native language. Textbook. –T.: Teacher, 2020. – 158 p.,
- 4.Akhmedova M.E., Rasulova G.K., Hamroyev G.H., Kuranbayeva X.A. Native language and reading literacy methodology. Textbook. “Zukhra Baraka Business” LLC. -T.: 2023. – 298 p.

